

Hypothesis Explaining Development of Squamous Cell Carcinoma During Infection with *Schistosoma Haematobium*

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Abstract:

Schistosome worms are blood-dwelling flukes that cause chronic infection in more than 200 million people and are thought to be responsible for 500,000 deaths annually. During infection with *Schistosoma haematobium*, eggs are deposited in the mucosa and submucosa of the bladder and lower ureters. Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the bladder is a long-term sequela of chronic infection. The mechanisms underlying the association between *S. haematobium* and SCC of the bladder are largely unknown, with all reports to date exclusively demonstrating epidemiological evidence linking *S. haematobium* infection with SCC of the bladder. Scientists

hypothesised that the parasite antigens might induce alterations in epithelial cells towards cancer. Scientists used Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cells and treated the cells in culture with *S. haematobium* total antigen (Sh). Results showed increased proliferation, increased S-phase and decreased apoptosis, as well as down-regulation of tumor suppressor p27 and up-regulation of anti-apoptotic molecule Bcl-2 (Botelho et al., 2009). Angiogenesis is defined as the formation of new blood vessels from preexisting ones and is recognized as a key event in cell proliferation and carcinogenesis and spread of malignant lesions (Dematei et al., 2017). *S. haematobium* is classified as a Group 1 carcinogen by the World Health Organization's International Agency for Research on Cancer (Hodderet al., 2000). Another factor that may play a major role in bladder carcinogenesis in schistosomiasis patients is the presence of continuous physical irritation and inflammation produced by *Schistosoma* eggs in the bladder mucosa. The adult *S. haematobium* worms inhabit the veins of the perivesical plexus, where the female lays eggs. Some eggs pass through the bladder mucosa and are excreted in the urine. Other eggs are trapped in the tissue. A chronic inflammatory reaction is initiated, with the invasion of histiocytes and other inflammatory cells into the bladder, the formation of granulomas and eventually fibrosis. In addition, the eruption of the eggs through the mucosa stimulates reparative urothelial hyperplasia and cell turnover (Rosin et al., 1994). In our article we try to explain possible mechanism of conversion normal cells into tumor cells from the position of karyogamic theory.

Keywords: *Carcinogens, Mechanism of carcinogenesis, Plasma membrane, Adhesion.*

Introduction

The existence of a link between urinary schistosomiasis (US) and bladder carcinoma was first suspected by C. Goebel in 1905. In 1911, A.R Ferguson, who was a professor of Pathology and Microbiology at the Faculty of Medicine in Cairo, published a more detailed survey from 40 autopsies, and reported a likely association of bladder carcinoma with granulomas caused by US. Subsequently, published results from several studies reinforced Ferguson's hypothesis. Moreover, in most countries where US was endemic, association of high prevalence of bladder carcinoma with US had been pointed out. A further circumstantial evidence was a higher prevalence of bladder squamous cell carcinoma in areas endemic for SU, whereas urothelial carcinomas were more prevalent in areas which were free of SU. However, evidence of a positive correlation between SU and bladder carcinoma was delivered only many decades later, following the results from case-control studies which were adjusted on age, sex, type of dwelling and tobacco consumption. During SU, the mechanisms underlying the onset of bladder carcinoma are still poorly understood due to the lack of any convenient animal model. Classically, two processes are thought to be involved. Chronic inflammation inside bladder would be caused by granulomas centered by eggs, and would result in a neoplastic evolution, after years. Moreover, alteration of the bladder dynamics would elicit urine stasis which in turn would cause repeated infection of bacterial or viral origin. Beside the high prevalence of squamous cell type, the natural history of bladder carcinomas caused by SU is similar to that of other malignant tumors of the bladder (Berry et al., 2017).

The initiation and progression of schistosomal bladder cancer is almost certainly a complex and multi-step process, involving the actions of the parasite, the host immune and tissue regenerative response, and possible participation of co-infections, micronutrients (e.g., vitamin A), and environmental exposures to carcinogens. Superimposed on these processes are background factors consisting of parasite genetic diversity, individual variations in intensity and

recurrence of infection, host genetic diversity (including polymorphic loci that affect immune responses or susceptibility to cancer), and sex differences in immune and urogenital biology. Though animal models will never recapitulate all aspects of these complex processes, appropriate application of such models will play an important role in efforts to isolate and characterize the pathways involved in schistosomal bladder cancer (Honeycutt et al., 2014).

Hypothesis

By our opinion the common mechanism of action of diametrically different carcinogens on target cell is the destruction of the plasmatic membrane (induction of the different size perforations) and consequently development of fusogeny-fusion of somatic cells, which is characteristics for any somatic cells and finally development of karyogamy.

Membrane fusion, merger of two membrane bilayers into one, is ubiquitous in cell biology. Fusion is a key stage in intracellular trafficking of membranes and proteins, including exocytosis. Enveloped viruses utilize fusion to enter cells. Cells fuse in fertilization, muscle and bone formation and maintenance. As fusion between protein-free bilayers, diverse biological fusion processes including well-characterized examples of intracellular, viral and cell-to-cell fusions, apparently start with a local merger of contacting leaflets of the membranes (referred to as hemifusion stalk) followed by opening of a nascent fusion pore (Kozlov & Chernomordik, 2015). In this pathway, fusion pore edge is lined by a bent lipid monolayer containing or not containing transmembrane protein domains (TMDs). While this fusion-through-hemifusion pathway seems to be widely accepted for most fusion processes (Chernomordik & Kozlov, 2005), it is still under debate in the case of SNARE-dependent intracellular membrane fusion where an alternative pathway starting from opening of an entirely proteinaceous channel-like fusion pore lined by SNARE TMDs is also considered (Chang & Jackson Meyer, 2015). Thus, the whole process of action of

fusogenic agents (parasitic antigens) could be represented in the following way:

1. Contact on a cell surface (umbrella cells of urinary bladder).
2. Modification or elimination of glycocalyx.
3. Disorganization of cytoplasmic membranes (by means of perforation).
4. Adhesion of two somatic cells.
5. Formation of common regions of cytoplasm between neighboring cells.
6. Formation of dikaryons, and
7. Fusion.

According to our assumptions, at the first stage of carcinogenesis (initiation) dikaryons (hetero- and homokaryons) and then mononuclear tetraploid (or hypotetraploid), precancerous cells are produced. At the promotion stage, after the influence of complete carcinogens or promoters on the tissue, where precancerous synkaryons preexist, the chromosomal aberrations of different types and genes amplifications may arise in these cells. In majority of cases, because of unsuccessful mitosis, elimination, perish of precancerous synkaryons probably takes place. In rare cases, in result of specific (reciprocal or unbalanced) translocation, duplications and following genes' amplification, these cells may undergo irreversible alterations and may transform into true tumor cells (Gogichadze et al., 2013). After fusogeny, together with dikaryons arise giant polynuclear cells, so called polykaryocytes. Polykaryocytes formed after endomitosis are functionally active. Unlike from these cells, polykaryocytes formed after fusogeny in most cases, are nonviable cellular formations, i.e., in the genetic respect, they probably are defective peculiar forms, with the lost abilities to enter in S-period of cellular cycle and mitosis and die quickly. Antibodies, like cytotoxic cells are known to induce perforations of different degrees of the plasma membranes of somatic cells, which can become a precondition for fusogenicity. In result of this, may form dikaryons with high oncological potency, and then, in case of synchronous mitosis or mechanical reunification of nuclei, they may

form mononuclear hybrid cell-precancerous cell, with tetraploid sets of chromosomes on initial stage of hybridization.

Conclusions

Here we are trying to explain possible mechanism of transformation normal cells into tumor ones in the case of Schistosomiasis from the view of karyogamic theory. Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the bladder is a long-term complication of chronic infection. The mechanisms underlying the association between *S. haematobium* and SCC of the bladder are largely unknown. Both adult and egg stage parasites secrete molecules, inducing changes in the host microenvironment that may be pro-carcinogenic. Influence of carcinogenic agents and factors on cells are adequate. In all probability, during the perforation of the cellular membranes, i.e., after the formation of pores, induced by carcinogenic agents released by parasite, the total negative charge of plasma membranes decreases and the cells develop the ability to come closer to each other, which frequently, especially upon coincidence of the perforated parts of this organelle, will probably be the prerequisite to a fusion process. At this stage together with multinucleated cellular structures, the binuclear-hetero- or homokaryons carriers of high carcinogenic potency are formed. As a result of karyogamy, i.e. after synchronous mitosis or simple mechanical assembly of nuclei heterokaryons (or homokaryons) mononuclear hybrid precancerous cells develop, with tetraploid (or hypotetraploid) set of chromosomes on initial stage of hybridization. Received as a result of somatic hybridization, the hybrid synkaryon is an initiated, immortal, precancerous cell, which exists in microorganism indefinitely for a long time. Fusion immediately doubles the number of chromosomes, thereby decreasing the chances that the loss of some chromosomes will kill the hybrid cell (synkaryon of stage 1). Further, in the processes of promotion and tumor progression, after the segregation of some chromosomes, there may arise tumorous cells with aneuploid or even hyperdiploid set of chromosomes.

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